

RECYCLING OF WIND TURBINE BLADES FOR FUSED FILAMENT FABRICATION FEEDSTOCK

A. Rahimizadeh¹, R. Henri², K. Fayazbakhsh³, and L. Lessard⁴

¹ Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, amirmohammad.rahimizadeh@mail.mcgill.ca

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, rodolphe.henri@mail.mcgill.ca

³ Aerospace Engineering, Ryerson University, Toronto, Canada, kazem@ryerson.ca, <https://www.ryerson.ca/aerospace/people/faculty/kazem-fayazbakhsh/>

⁴ Department of Mechanical Engineering, McGill University, Montreal, Canada, larry.lessard@mcgill.ca, <https://www.mcgill.ca/mecheng/people/staff/larrylessard>

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ABSTRACT

The wind energy industry is one of the fastest-growing application sectors of composites, where reinforcement fibers are used in the manufacturing of light rotor blades. Considering the limited lifetime of turbine blades, a growing number of wind turbines will start to be decommissioned. Turbine blades are generally landfilled at their end-of-life, which highly impacts the environment. This paper proposes a systematic scheme combining mechanical recycling and 3D printing to recycle the valuable constituents of the scrap blades and reuse them in a Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) process with the aim of improving the mechanical performance of 3D printed components. Mechanical grinding integrated with a double sieving mechanism is utilized to recover the reinforcement fibers. Tensile test specimens with 5 wt% fiber content are fabricated from the recycled fibers and plastic pellets and their mechanical properties as well as internal microstructure are investigated. The results demonstrate an improvement of 16% and 10 % in the elastic modulus and ultimate strength of the reinforced composite filament as compared to the commercially available pure PLA filament. As well, a Young's modulus of 3.35 GPa was observed for the FFF fabricated samples, which is an 8% increase relative to pure PLA samples.

1 INTRODUCTION

The superior mechanical properties of composite materials provide an exiting opportunity to build structures that are lightweight and of high strength, characteristics that have led to many engineering applications for composites [1-4]. The wind energy industry represents one of the fastest growing application sectors of composites, where reinforcement fibers, such as fiberglass or carbon fibers, a plastic polymer, such as polyester or epoxy, and a core material are used to build strong and compliant rotor blades [5]. The dramatic growth of wind industry over the past 20 years has resulted in an extensive amount of end-of-life rotor blades. Current routes to dispose of turbine blades at their end-of-life involve landfill and incineration, methods that are associated with environmental impact [6, 7]. Given the non-biodegradable nature of turbine blades, recent environmental legislation has increasingly demanded for the recycling and replacing of turbine blades in the near future [5, 6, 8]. Recent research efforts in the area of wind energy have been focused on the development of sustainable methods for the recycling and reuse of rotor blades. To address this pivotal challenge, scientists have resorted to chemical and pyrolysis techniques to recover glass fibers from end-of-life

turbine blades [6]. Despite the high mechanical properties of the recycled fibers, these techniques show little promise in terms of commercialisation due to the use of hazardous chemicals and/or excessive cost.

Recent studies have shown that composite materials can be systematically designed and used to produce strong and stiff feedstocks for Additive Manufacturing (AM) processes [9-12]. AM represents a class of fabrication techniques where a layer-upon-layer method is used to build a part from a 3D model [13-15]. AM enables the fabrication of components with complex geometries, those that are unachievable using traditional manufacturing techniques [16]. Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) is the most widely used 3D printing process due to its simplicity, low cost, and minimal wastage [17]. While extremely efficient, FFF parts are generally made of pure thermoplastic material, which results in low strength and stiffness, dominant factors in contributing to their limited structural performance [18-22].

In one interesting study, Shofner et al. [23] used ABS matrix to develop nano-fiber reinforced composites through FFF. The filament was made of single-walled carbon nanotubes and ABS plastic. With the newly developed filament, they observed 40% and 60% increase in the tensile strength and Young's modulus of the 3D printed parts, respectively. Zhong et al. [24] incorporated short glass fibers into ABS matrix to produce FFF filament. Their results showed that the parts made of glass fiber reinforced filament feature higher tensile strength relative to pure ABS. In a more recent study, Ning et al. [17] investigated the mechanical performance of FFF 3D printed parts made of virgin carbon fiber reinforced ABS filament. ASTM D638 standard was followed to prepare tensile test specimens with different fiber content, i.e. 3, 5, 7.5, 10, and 15 wt%. Compared with the pure ABS specimens, an improvement in the flexural and tensile strength was attained by increasing the fiber content from 3 to 5 wt%. However, a further increase in the fiber content from 5 wt% to 10 wt% resulted in a reduction of the tensile strength. This reduction in properties is attributed to the pores that develop during the extrusion and printing process of the filaments with high fiber content.

This investigation examines the feasibility of using fiber glass scrap from wind turbine blades as reinforcement in thermoplastic filaments for 3D printing to achieve the following: addressing the challenging issue of wind turbine blade scrap that is increasingly growing every year; and improving mechanical properties of 3D printed thermoplastic parts without the need of adding high cost virgin fibers. In this paper, the ASTM D638 standard test method is followed to properly characterize tensile strength of 3D printed parts out of pure PLA and PLA reinforced with fiberglass. In the following sections, first, a systematic methodology is proposed integrating mechanical recycling and filament extrusion to manufacture PLA filaments reinforced with fiberglass. Then, specimen geometry, configuration, and testing procedure are described as per ASTM D638. Next, the specimen manufacturing, including 3D printing process and design parameters, is described extensively. Experimental testing is performed and the tensile strength for different filament materials is obtained. Finally, the performance of the 3D printed specimens with pure and reinforced PLA is discussed and recommendations for future research are presented.

2 METHODOLOGY

One of the causes of environmental pollution is landfill of wind turbine blades. This work proposes to recycle the turbine blades at their end-of-life and reincorporate them into thermoplastic FFF filaments. The major aspects of the approach that are taken here rest on the integration of mechanical grinding and filament extrusion to transform the recycled glass fibers into commercial FFF feedstock material. Figure 1 depicts the current methodology, where the key steps are briefly described below:

1. A mechanical recycling method combining grinding and a double sieving process is performed to recover the glass fibers from the scrap blades. Since the diameter of the 3D printer nozzle used here is 0.4 mm, the double sieving operation ensures a supply of fibers with a length generally below 0.4 mm, a characteristic essential for filaments with high processability.

2. The mixture of the PLA pellets and the fibers are placed in a dehydrator machine for a drying process of 4 hours at 60°C. This dehydration process reduces the moisture content of the pellets that could generate voids during the extrusion process.
3. To generate the Recycled Glass Fiber Reinforced Filament (RGFRF) for FFF, the raw materials obtained in step 2 are first fed into a twin-screw extruder connected to a pelletizer to produce glass fiber reinforced pellets. Following the initial extrusion, the pellets are re-dried and fed into a single screw extruder to produce RGFRF. The extruder screw speed, the die temperature as well as the winder speed are tuned to attain a filament with consistent diameter of 1.75 mm. A laser micrometer with an accuracy of $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ is used along with the extruder to monitor the filament diameter.
4. Tensile properties of a single filament made out of pure PLA, as a baseline, and reinforced filaments are compared. In addition, tensile coupons are manufactured as per ASTM D638 type I out of pure PLA filament and RGFRF. Tensile testing is performed on the coupons and the resulting mechanical properties are compared to evaluate the performance of the newly developed filament.

Figure 1: The proposed methodology for recycling of wind turbine blades.

2.1 Mechanical recycling

In the present study, recycled glass fibers with an average length of 0.1-0.4 mm are obtained from grinding a turbine blade made of glass fiber reinforced epoxy composite. Since the nozzle diameter of the printer used in this investigation is 0.4 mm, this range of fiber length ensures a high processability for the proposed filament. Longer fiber lengths lead to the possibility of clogging the 3D printer output nozzle. As observed in Figure 2, a three-stage recycling procedure is used here to obtain the fibers for the filament extrusion: First, the blades are cut down into 20×20 cm pieces using a band saw and then fed into a grinder machine (ECO-WOLF, INC.) consisting of a hammer mill system and a classifier with a hole size of 3 mm. Following the first granulation process, visual inspection microscopy of the recycled materials demonstrates a mixture of resin powder and fibers, resulting in a fiber length range of 0.1-2.5 mm. To further classify the recycled materials, a double sieving mechanism is used and two

grades of granulated material are obtained. The granulated blade obtained from the first grinding process is sieved through a stainless-steel screen with a hole size of 0.1 mm. The larger-sized recycled material is then re-fed in the sieve for the second sieving operation to extract more fine fibers that are in the desirable length range.

Figure 2: The proposed three-stage grinding methodology for the mechanical recycling of wind turbine blades.

2.2 Filament extrusion

The glass fiber reinforce filament is fabricated through a double melt extrusion process of PLA pellets (Ingeo 4043D, Natureworks LLC, Blair, Nebraska) and 5 wt% recycled glass fibers. The pellets are first dried at 60 for 4 hours and then mixed in a twin-screw extruder (Leistritz ZSE18HP-40D, Nuremberg, Germany) to produce glass fiber reinforced pellets. The reinforced pellets are then re-dried and fed into a single screw extruder (FilaFab, D3D Innovations Limited, Bristol, UK) to produce RGFRF. The extrusion parameters including the screw speed, the speed of the winder as well as the die temperature are properly adjusted to achieve a 1.75 ± 0.05 mm filament, a suitable diameter and tolerance for the 3D printing process. The extrusion temperature, screw speed, die diameter and winder speed are set to 210 °C, 25 rpm, 2 mm and 1 rpm, respectively.

2.3 Specimens design and manufacturing

ASTM D638-14 standard is followed here to characterize the tensile properties of 3D printed parts made of RGFRF and pure PLA. As per ASTM D638, five different types of tensile test specimen are suggested. As a result, five pure PLA and reinforced specimens with a total thickness of 3.36 mm and 0° raster orientation are prepared using a Prusa i3 Mk2S printer for the test. Manufacturing process and design parameters are summarized in Table 1. The mass value of the specimens is measured by a precision balance. Tensile tests on the 3D printed samples are conducted in a test machine (312 Q tensile machine, Testresources) with a 10 KN force transducer capacity and a 5 mm/min testing speed.

Manufacturing parameter	Value	Manufacturing parameter	Value
Print direction	XYZ	Nozzle diameter (mm)	0.4
Raster angle	0	Nozzle temperature (°C)	215
Layer height (mm)	0.14	Cooling	No fan cooling
Bed temperature (°C)	60	Infill (%)	100
Print speed (mm/min)	2400	Filament diameter (mm)	1.75

Table 1: Manufacturing and design parameters for specimen 3D printing.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 illustrates the probability distribution of the fiber length evaluated by measuring the length of at least 300 fibers from each grade of granulated material. As seen, after the second sieve operation,

most of the fibers feature lengths in the range of 0.15-0.18 mm, thus ensuring the processability of the fibers for the use in the FFF process. Although it is difficult to differentiate the fibers in terms of shape characteristics, it could be concluded from visual inspection that after the second sieve operation, fiber bundles are separated, and fibers are in a better refined state. Resin residue in the form of powder is also visible in the recycle.

Figure 3: Probability distribution for fiber length of three grades of recycled fibers obtained from (a) grinding of blades; (b) first sieve operation; and (c) second sieve operation.

3.1 FFF 3D printing filaments

A typical stress-strain curve for both the pure PLA filament and RGFRF, along with their tensile properties, are shown in Figure 4. The results demonstrate an increase of 10% (51.66 to 56.63 MPa) and 16% (3.17 to 3.6 GPa) in the Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS) and tensile modulus of RGFRF relative to pure PLA filament. A larger variability is observed for the strength results of the reinforced composite filament, which could be ascribed to the diameter variations in the filament as well as, variations in the surface quality of the filament due to the presence of long fibers in the compound. On the other hand, the variability of the stiffness results for the composite filament is comparable to that of the pure PLA filament and all the samples showed higher stiffness relative to the pure PLA samples. However, the precise control of the filament diameter and carefully separating the fibers longer than the 3D printer nozzle, could result in lower strength variations.

Figure 4: The tensile properties of the extruded pure PLA filament and reinforced filament: (a) test set-up; (b) stress-strain curve; (c) UTS; (d) Young's modulus.

The microstructures of the pure PLA filament and RGFRF along the transverse and longitudinal directions are shown in Figure 5. The PLA filament shows smooth and round edges with no visible air bubbles, indicating the successful removal of the moisture content during the dehydration process. The RGFRF, on the other hand, contains relatively small internal voids that are distributed throughout the filament. The double extrusion process increases the likelihood of moisture absorption by the PLA and consequent air bubble formation probability during the extrusion process. As observed in the transverse cross section of RGFRF, glass fibers are visible in the reinforced filament and are well distributed throughout the cross section. The longitudinal cross section reveals that the fibers are generally well aligned in the directions of extrusion.

Figure 5: SEM images of pure PLA filament and RGFRF: (a) The transverse cross section of pure PLA filament; (b) the longitudinal cross section of pure PLA filament; (c) the transverse cross section of RGFRF; and (d) the longitudinal cross section of RGFRF.

3.2 FFF 3D printed tensile test specimens

Figure 6 shows the representative engineering stress-strain curves for the tensile test samples. It was observed that the 3D printed composite samples feature a Young's modulus enhanced by about 8% (3.12 to 3.35 GPa) compared with pure PLA specimens, while there was no meaningful increase in UTS. The elastic stiffness of the 3D printed specimens is slightly lower compared to the individual filaments, e.g. 1.5% and 7% reduction for pure PLA and composite coupons, respectively. This could be attributed to the 3D printing process that introduces some defects and higher quantity of large voids, e.g. interlayer voids, within the samples.

Figure 6: The tensile properties of the pure PLA and composite tensile test specimens: (a) test set-up; (b) stress-strain curve; (c) UTS; (d) Young's modulus.

To explore the porosity of the coupons, SEM images from the fracture surface of the pure PLA and reinforced specimens are examined. As seen in Figure 7, the reinforced samples feature larger internal voids, which are likely a result of nozzle clogging due to the presence of fibers with larger length compared to the nozzle diameter. The presence of ruptured fibers demonstrates an effective load transfer capacity between the PLA matrix and the recycled fibers. The SEM images show that some fibers have been pulled out of the PLA due to insufficient interfacial strength. This could be attributed to the variation of the epoxy residue on the fibers surface, which lowers the possibility of the molecular interactions and thus hydrogen bonding at the interface.

Figure 7: The fracture surface SEM of the 3D printed specimens: (a) pure PLA; and (b) with recycled glass fibers.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study describes a methodology integrating mechanical recycling and FFF 3D printing as a potential solution to the problem of composite waste from wind turbine blades. The scrap turbine blades are first ground and sieved to obtain processable recycled glass fibers for application in 3D printing. The ground fibers are then mixed with PLA, a biodegradable polymer, to extrude glass fiber reinforced filament. To demonstrate the mechanical performance of the newly developed filament, tensile test specimens with 5 wt% fiber content are fabricated and the effect on tensile properties, namely Young's modulus and tensile strength, are studied. The reinforced filament features a glass transition temperature comparable to that of pure PLA filament. However, a slight increase in the crystallinity of the reinforced filament is observed with respect to pure PLA filament. The results show that the addition of 5 wt% recycled fibers leads to an increase of 16% and 10% in the Young's modulus and strength of the pure PLA filament, respectively. Mechanical tests on FFF fabricated coupons demonstrate an increase of 8% in the Young's modulus relative to pure PLA samples, while there is no significant improvement in tensile strength. This level of performance would translate in the potential of application of recycled glass fibers from wind turbine blades into the 3D printing industry. SEM micrographs from the fracture surface of FFF composite samples show the presence of ruptured fibers confirming an effective load transfer between the PLA matrix and the recycled fibers. To better understand the interfacial strength between the recycled fibers and the thermoplastic matrix, further study is required to compare the interface of PLA with virgin and recycled fibers. Another aspect that requires further investigation is the effect of fiber content on the interfacial bonding and the mechanical properties of the 3D printed samples.

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